

PBL Student Projects and Sustainable Development Goals: A Case Study

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Abstract

Working with the Sustainable Development Goals can be a highly motivating factor in Problem Based Learning, especially if the solutions produced can be used afterwards and have an actual impact on people and communities. This paper describes how three engineering students from Aalborg University, Denmark, collaborated with the South African Organisation Green Shoots on bringing IT-supported Math education out to some of the most disadvantaged learners from townships and rural areas of the Western Cape. The project provided the Danish students with a unique learning experience and have a lasting impact on the communities involved. While the content of the project focused on bringing IT-supported Math education to learners in previously disadvantaged areas around the Western Cape, the project also provided valuable insight into how such students' projects, where the outcomes benefit people and communities suffering from socio-economic challenges e.g. poverty, can be carried out. In addition to demonstrate that such projects are actually possible, we studied three critical aspects: How to ensure a good fit between learning objectives and project outcome, how to ensure that the project creates value for the partner organisation and communities, and how to ensure that the projects can be conducted without overloading the university supervisors. We believe that student projects focusing on SDGs have a big potential in terms of providing highly motivating student projects yet at the same time contribute to a better world through solutions that are being used even afterwards. However, our study was just a single case with one group of three students. We hope it will serve as inspiration for larger studies, where more quantitative data could be gathered in terms of how to establish a good framework around such projects, and in order to demonstrate the value for students and societies.

Keywords: Problem Based Learning; Sustainability; Student engagement in learning.

1 Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are defined by the United Nations as a universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet and ensure that all people enjoy peace and prosperity. They came into effect in January 2016 and will continue to guide UNDP policy and funding until 2030 (United Nations Development Program, 2016). The goals were agreed upon among all the countries in the world.

There is a big potential for students in working with the SDGs: There are many motivating and interesting problems to work on, it is possible to make a positive difference for the world, and the students can learn a lot from working in a context that is often very different from what they have otherwise experienced. Moreover, at least at a high level it fits very well in a Problem Based Learning (PBL) setting, such as the model practiced at Aalborg University (AAU) (Kolmos et al., 2004), where there is a big emphasis on analyzing and understanding the problem at hand before designing a relevant solution. The PBL setting, where the problem guides the choice of methods and tools, also provides a good starting point for developing solutions that can actually be used and applied and thus create value for collaboration partners, communities and societies.

Student projects focusing on the SDGs can take many shapes and forms: They can focus on students solving local problems in their own communities or through international collaboration; They can be mono- or interdisciplinary; And they can happen either within academia, or in collaboration with different kinds of partners including NGOs, industry, public bodies and communities. In this project we search to explore how projects can be carried out in an international setting in a collaboration between students and an NGO who can use the developed solution in achieving their goals of improving education among learners in the Western Cape province of South Africa.

The paper searches to answer the research question: How can PBL student projects support the development of the SDGs through collaboration with local partners? In particular, we search to understand how this can be done in a way that (1) ensures that the students learn what they are required to learn according to their learning objectives, (2) ensures that the solutions developed have sufficient value for the local organizations to justify their investment of time and resources, and (3) does not lead to an overload of the supervisors involved in the project. This research question is further motivated in the Background Section.

The main contribution of the paper is a small case demonstrating how all the three points listed above were achieved, as well as an identification of points that are crucial in order for the points to be fulfilled. This is done by analyzing all steps of the project, from development of the project proposal to the actual handover of the final product.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: The background section provides the context, and the research gap is identified. We also present the theoretical framework for the project and the research methodology used. In the Analysis section, we describe and analyze the different steps of carrying out the project, which leads to the Discussion section where we discuss the most important findings. We summarize our findings in the Conclusion section, which also contains suggestions for further work in the field.

2 Background

2.1 Context

Aalborg University has been applying the Problem Based Learning model since 1974, and during the last years intensified the work with sustainability in engineering education through a number of student projects (Krogh-Hansen et al., 2014) as well as a number of research studies, e.g. (Smink et al., 2018) which concludes that both among students in sustainability programmes and among other students, very few (19,7% and 13,1%) find themselves well prepared in relation to social responsibility. The study concludes that one of the ways to go is to establish problem-based learning environments, where students work in cross-programme project groups to deal with a sustainability problem that calls for both disciplines, but also that structures need to be in place in order to find each other and release this potential. However, we would add that another important aspect of this is to match companies/organisations with students, in order to find students with the right competences and learning objectives in order to help solving the problems at hand. The match between the problems that motivate the project and the learning objectives of the students is important also to achieve a good alignment between what the students learn, and on which basis they are actually examined. This is well known and described as constructive alignment (Biggs and Tang, 2011).

Another study – also a case where students work on a sustainability project – was carried out in (Dahms, 1998). The paper focuses especially on the challenges in virtual collaboration throughout the project period. Challenges in international and virtual collaboration are also described in the recent papers such as (Pedersen et. al., 2018). Here, projects are carried out in collaboration between students from different countries, in collaboration with companies, and based on real problems. While these projects do not necessarily have their focus on sustainability, they do have the components of both virtual collaboration and collaboration between students and companies. Their preliminary findings also include that it is important that learning objectives are aligned, that the virtual collaboration is facilitated, and that the companies actually benefit from participation, so they are interested in continuing the collaboration.

In this paper, we investigate an example of a collaborative project, where students work on solving real-life problems with respect to improving the life conditions of some of the most disadvantaged children in the world. This is a challenging setting for the students, partly because the context is so different from what they are used to, and partly because the collaboration has a large virtual component. In particular, our research aims at determining major barriers for such projects to be established and executed as well as good practices for making such projects successful for both students and collaboration partners.

The project itself was centred around practical issues faced by Green Shoots, a Not-for-profit organisation, which has developed and is now operating an IT system for math education that is being used in South Africa,

predominantly in the Western Cape. The system is implemented as a website, requiring a reliable internet connection in order to function properly. For many schools this is not problem, as they have a working internet connection, but this is not the situation for all schools in South Africa, particularly in rural areas.

In order to help disadvantaged children in rural areas, Green Shoots came up with a solution to this problem. Green Shoots divides schools into two categories, online schools with a functioning internet connection and offline schools with an unreliable internet connection. Since offline schools are not able to access the website on the internet, a computer is placed at the school that provides a local version of the website. This means that access to educational material is not dependent on the state of the internet connection.

The benefit of this solution for offline schools, is that children will always be able to practice their math. As Green Shoots found, there were however downsides to this type of solution.

Regularly updates to the IT system has to be made by Green Shoots, this includes adding new children to the system at the beginning of the school year and updating educational content and tests. For online schools this is simple, an update can be made to the central system, the website, which will be available immediately to all online schools. It's not as easy for offline schools. Since the offline schools are not connected to the internet, they can't be updated centrally, meaning that each offline school has to be updated manually. This was typically done by using a remote desktop application or physically driving out to the school.

These problems made maintenance of an offline school very expensive and hard to scale, causing Green Shoots to limit the amount of offline schools, meaning that disadvantaged children in rural areas could not be helped as effectively.

The solution developed for this problem was a software application that would monitor the state of an offline schools' unreliable internet connection and determine the most opportune time to communicate with a central system. Once communication was available, updates to offline schools could be sent, and updates to the local IT system could be made automatically. This solution gave Green Shoots the same flexibility for offline schools as online schools, reducing maintenance costs and allowing Green Shoots to support schools in rural areas with disadvantaged children.

2.2 Research contribution

Based on the background and research described above, we identify two important research questions when it comes to PBL student projects, where students work on the SDGs in collaboration with partner organisations that are not physically located close to the university:

- How do we ensure that the students learning objectives are fulfilled, i.e. that there is a good match between the problem to be solved and the learning objectives?
- How to ensure that the project – either the process or the end product - creates value for the partner organisation?

Based on our own experience with both sustainability and international student projects, we add one additional research question, which is also critical to answer in order to develop projects that are sustainable in the longer run:

- How to ensure that these projects can be carried out without overloading the supervisors in either phase of the project work?

2.3 Methodology

The paper is based on the study of a single case of collaboration between the South African not-for-profit organization Green Shoots and a group of master degree students on the 8th semester (4th year) of the engineering program of Networks and Distributed Systems. This paper is co-authored by the key stakeholders in the collaboration (students, university supervisor and contacts in Green Shoots), and the experiences described are based on systematic evaluations collected throughout the duration of the project and collaboration process. The structure of the analysis follows this systematic approach by presenting the different phases of the project, and for each phase containing:

- A description of how that phase was carried out
- An evaluation of what worked well and not so well
- A summary of the most important learning points from this phase

3 Analysis

In this section we describe the different phases and the experience throughout the different phases. We focus on all learning points, but with special emphasis on covering the research questions presented in the Background section.

The phases cover the project, but also the whole PBL learning experience: Initially, the students observe and analyse the problem, leading to a problem analysis and formulation that is discussed with the stakeholders. Based on the problem formulation, a solution is designed and implemented in close collaboration with the stakeholders. After this, the project is evaluated and graded, but in this case the students put in additional efforts after the exam to ensure the project was ready for deployment and went on a second study trip to ensure a good handover process.

It is important to note that both students, supervisor and Green Shoots took active part in all the phases, however the first phase of setting up the collaboration was done before the students got involved, and the two last phases of finalizing the project and handover was done directly between the students and Green Shoots without much involvement of the supervisor.

3.1 Setting up the collaboration (January-October 2017)

Description: The initial contact was established when the academic supervisor of the project met the Director of Green Shoots at a learning conference in Philadelphia during December 2016, more than a year before the actual student project started up. Green Shoots was running an IT-based system for Math Education, deployed already at that time to more than 200 schools in the Western Cape, where the learners were given access to interactive math education, while the teachers and school districts could collect valuable data to monitor progress and identify challenges. However, the current technical solution did not support schools with poor Internet connectivity in a scalable way. This seemed like a good match for students in the Department of Electronic Systems, working with computer networks and distributed systems. Based on this initial contact, the dialogue continued through Skype meetings and exchange of emails, which helped to narrow down the selection of students from a semester with relevant backgrounds and learning objectives, until a final project proposal was ready in the spring 2017. Already at this stage, it was identified that the project had a better fit with students of the spring semester, and it was decided to aim for having the project during spring 2018. In AAU this semester runs from February to May, with exams in June. However, in this case the students onboarded the project already in November 2017, and the final handover took place after the exams, i.e. in July 2018.

Reflections and experiences: At this point no students were involved, and at the end of the phase a good project proposal was in place. As such, one of the critical challenges had at least initially been overcome by matching company needs with students with relevant backgrounds and learning objectives. However, in our case this happened only because the right people met at the right time: Otherwise it could have been hard to identify such a match. It requires a good insight into each other's domains to match problem and potential solution before an actual problem analysis has been carried out. Another critical factor is the time it took from initial contact to starting up the project, which was partly due to this phase taking so long: This implied that Green Shoots were already looking at alternative solutions once the students started working on the project. While it took time, we think it was crucial that we managed to establish clear expectations as to the goals of the project, commitments of the time required from all sides, and a mutual understanding of the perceived value for all partners. On a final note, we found that this is a phase where the supervisor has to invest more resources than in other student projects: On the other hand, we believe that if the same collaboration can be continued in the longer term, the workload will be less once the collaboration has been established.

3.2 Recruiting the students (November 2017)

Description: At Aalborg University, students select project topics during the first week of the semester (in February), and on the particular study in Networks and Distributed systems there are often many more project proposals than student groups. However, in this case it was agreed that the students would visit Green Shoots in South Africa already in January (before the semester and courses start), and together with the need for fundraising for the travel this created a need for choosing the project much earlier. In fact, the students were selected already in the beginning of November.

Reflections and experiences: This is a more or less hand-held solution, which worked well in practice, but it is challenging how the semester start and project selection process is usually carried out: Usually the groups are formed by students, where the policy is that “no group is formed before all groups are formed”, and here some students can shortcut that process by settling in the group so early. Also, at this time the students do not know what alternative projects they could select from. A final hand-held aspect is that there is no policy in place as to which students can apply: One could imagine a situation, where only students with a certain level could choose these projects, to ensure that the university remains an attractive collaboration partner: This reflects the balance between doing projects for the benefit of the students, and for the benefits of the collaborating organizations. One of the drawbacks of such hand-held solutions is that they put an additional workload on the supervisors. With a more streamlined “standard” procedure in place, we believe this additional workload could be significantly reduced if not eliminated.

3.3 Field visit to get a problem understanding and scoping (January 2018)

Description: The purpose of the first field visit was to identify the problem(s) to solve, and to scope the project accordingly together with the relevant stakeholders. This happened through visiting not only Green Shoots, but also their collaboration partners (e.g. software developers) and schools, where it was important both to see and understand the conditions the schools were working under, and to speak to the teachers and learn about their experiences. The visit lasted a week, and took place in the last week of January: This is just before the start of the semester, and thus collisions with other learning activities were avoided. Only two students were able to participate due to VISA issues. The supervisor also participated. Based on previous experience, the physical meeting was also used to establish a project plan for the collaboration, to be sure there was a mutual understanding of milestones, deliverables and communication throughout the project. The study trip was financed through a mix of self-contributions from the students, internal grants from the university, and grants from external foundations.

Reflections and experiences: First, the possibility to experience the context of the system and get a first-hand experience of the challenges and constraints was non-negotiable, as was understanding the value of Green Shoots interventions and consequently the real-world impact of the project beyond being a paper exercise. Establishing this was an important extension of the already mentioned points about clear goals, and understandings of the value and commitment for all parties. Secondly, having face-to-face meetings and establishing a good relationship between the teams was very important in order to be able to work together remotely later on. These findings are well in line with the experiences from (Dahms, 1998) and (Pedersen et. al., 2018).

3.4 Virtual collaboration phase (February-June 2018)

Description: The virtual collaboration phase was throughout the duration of the project, officially from February to May (where the project report was to be handed in), but in reality continuing throughout July to ensure that the product was ready for handover. A joint virtual communication platform (Asana), which was already used by Green Shoots was established from the beginning and used for ongoing updates as well as regular conference calls. However, the need for communication went beyond updates and ongoing feedback/discussions. In particular, there was a need for establishing a technical sandbox environment for testing purposes, and also the project scope was adjusted over time due to other development projects around Green Shoots. While being able to follow the communication through Asana, the supervisor was not in general a part of the communication that happened directly between the students and Green Shoots. Instead, the supervisor helped the students with both technical aspects of the course, and with advice on how to handle

the collaboration with Green Shoots. At some point, where the students were busy with other study activities of the semester, the supervisor played a more active role.

Reflections and experiences: The virtual collaboration phase went well overall, but not without challenges. First, in many traditional projects the problem and context remain static throughout the solution development, which was not the case here because Green Shoots in parallel was working on developing and improving the systems. This required an agile approach, but also close communication in order to shape the interfaces of the project with the parallel development activities. Having learning objectives which includes the process of developing solutions (rather than just the technical aspects of the solution) is crucial in order to credit the students for this effort. We believe this is an important aspect of engineering education. We also found that the way of working with the supervisor remaining “on the side” worked well, and it kept the communication quite simple. With respect to the ongoing communication with Green Shoots, and the assistance in setting up the right technical tools, we found this to be a crucial investment of time/resources from Green Shoots in order to achieve results, which are useful afterwards. However, communication is also an aspect where the students could have been better trained, especially the necessity to continue the communication even in periods where other study activities caused progress to slow down.

3.5 Official project closing, reporting and evaluation (June 1018)

Description: The project was handed in as any other student project at AAU, and as usual documented through both code and report. Based on the report, an oral examination was held where the students presented the project and discussed it. The project was evaluated and graded according to the normal learning objectives of the semester, where the theme is “Distributed Systems Design”. The learning objectives covers system design in a broad sense, which also makes it possible to give credits for the context analysis that the students spend so much effort on. Also, the study regulation refers to “system design methodologies” without being specific, which allows a focus on agile design and development methodologies as was applied in this project. The students note that much of the added value from participating in the project was not so much related to the technical aspects, but rather the skills related to communication, organisation, collaboration, and an appreciation of understanding the context a problem resides in. However, these aspects are not really covered by the learning objectives of the semester.

Reflections and experiences: As demonstrated in previous research (e.g. constructive alignment, see Section 2.1), it is important that the objectives of the project are aligned with the learning objectives of the semester. The project here turned out to be well aligned with the learning objectives, but there is a real risk that the initial phase of the project leads to different conclusions: For example, the analysis conducted after the field trip might conclude that there is a need for different methods than initially expected. If the learning objectives are defined too narrow or too specific, this can lead to a situation with lack of alignment between project objectives and learning objectives, potentially forcing the students to choose between satisfying the project requirements (and make a project that is useful for the partner) or to satisfy the learning objectives (and make a project for which they can receive a high grade). We are speculating if this would be less of a challenge with long-term collaborations, where the university supervisor(s) might have established knowledge of the problems to work on through previous projects. We would also suggest to think into study regulations learning objectives related to the more collaborative aspects or sustainability, which would make it easier to accommodate this kind of projects.

3.6 Finalizing the project after official hand-in (June-July 2018)

Description: From a student’s perspective the development process from the beginning was different compared to a typical student project. In a typical student project, the focus of implementing a system is to show new ideas, meaning that features are prioritised ahead of other important properties in a software application, such as stability. The focus during this type of project had to be different since the final product would actually be used after the project. This was a large motivating factor for the students, since projects would often be forgotten about the day after the last exam. The fact that the priority had to be stability rather than features was clear from the beginning, based on an understanding of the ethos of Green Shoots. Based on discussions it was clear that both parties preferred a small but well-working solution. Once the students

officially finished the project with the hand-in of their report, the system was prepared for implementation at Green Shoots. The students did this by working through their holiday, in order to prepare the developed solution for a production environment at Green Shoots. After hand-in the students focused on improving the stability of the application. This came at the cost of some features, that were removed, since they weren't considered mature enough. The removal of features was a hard decision, but it was made to reduce the complexity of the solution. The supervisor was generally not involved at this stage, and all communication happened directly between the students and Green Shoots.

Reflections and experiences: The time after the hand-in and before the field visit and handover was critical. It gave the students time to reflect on the system, without the stress of other exams, and allowed complete focus on the developed solution. On the other hand, this perception from the students also demonstrates that there is some difference between the requirements for the exam, and the requirements in terms of a well-functioning product at the end. It was agreed, however, that the solution of working through the summer was good, and that such a commitment from the students is fair in order to participate in a project like this. There was no additional workload for the supervisor during this phase.

3.7 Field visit and handover (July 2018)

Description With a stable and final version of the solution in hand, another field visit to South Africa took place – this time without participation of the supervisor. A test implementation of the newly developed solution was made at an offline school, in order to demonstrate the features of the solution. The students also brought documentation explaining how to use the solution, and showed how to use the system, so that it could be brought to use by Green Shoots. The solution was demonstrated to all members of the Green Shoots team, in order to show how the investment of time in a student project could pay off. The field visit again had a duration of one week. Again, the trip was financed through a mix of internal and external sources and self-contribution from students.

Reflections and experiences: The purpose of this field visit was to hand-over the solution, which happened successfully. An important aspect of this was that Green Shoots was able to take independent ownership of the solution, and as such would not rely on the student group for further integration and development. Having two intercontinental study trips as part of a semester project might not seem as a solution that can be replicated in all places, but we found that also the second trip was important to ensure a good hand-over of the project to ensure that Green Shoots could take ownership of the project from here. One way of reducing the need for travel could be that not all students participate in both trips, and/or to organize the trips so they combine hand-over of one project (or sub-project) and starting up the next (sub-) project. On the other hand, the students found it very valuable and learningful to be able to follow a project all the way through from initial investigation to implementation and hand-over.

4 Discussion

Overall, we consider the project to be a success, which demonstrates that it is indeed possible to carry out student projects related to the SDGs, which make a difference for communities, add value for the collaboration partners, and fit the learning objectives of the students. On the other hand, we also experienced some challenges, of which many relate to the structural setup of projects, and might require more systemic changes to be really resolved. In the following we will focus the discussion on the points related to the research questions.

With respect to the learning objectives, this case demonstrates an example where there is a very good fit between the learning objectives of the students, and the project defined based on the needs of Green Shoots. To a large extent this was made possible through a thorough process of collaboration setup and project scoping, and through identifying a relevant semester project for the work. As mentioned above, it is important that the learning objectives are sufficiently broad and flexible to manage that the project might be adjust over time, both as a consequence of the initial analysis conducted, or because it is impacted by other projects/processes within the partner organisations. We believe that an effort where learning goals can explicitly include sustainability and/or international collaboration can also support that the students get due

credits for their work, but again we believe that flexibility is a key word, since we also need to respond to the project possibilities that are coming up.

With respect to the value creation for the communities and partner organisations, we found several factors to be of high importance. First of all, it is important that students and partner organisations develop a mutual understanding of the outcome of the project, how the outcomes will be used, and how the collaboration will work. It is also important that all partners are willing to commit time and resources. Second, the field visit – while being one of the least scalable aspects of the setup – was important to develop the relationship between all partners, and to provide the students with first-hand understanding of the context. When looking at how the value is created in relation to the time invested, we found that in our case both the university supervisor and Green Shoots invested quite a lot of time in setting up the collaboration. We believe that a key to reduce this overhead can be to have long-term collaborations, where more groups of students – in parallel and/or in continuation – can contribute with different parts of solutions. This could also facilitate the collaboration between disciplines as mentioned in (Smink et al., 2018). We leave it as an open question whether this kind of projects should be open for all students, or just selected students who demonstrate the capabilities and commitments to ensure a significant output for the partner organisation.

With respect to the workload of supervisors, we find that the setup with direct communication between partner organisation and students worked well, and for the supervisor the workload during the execution of the project were not more than that of any other student project. However, more time was spent during setting up the collaboration, project proposal, and during the initial problem understanding (including the study trip). In addition to seeing this as a long-term investment in a partnership as discussed above, maybe a broker function at the university could help to match problems with relevant studies and semesters: However, doing so requires some technical insights which will likely involve potential supervisors. Also, the value of early involvement of supervisors in order to establish personal relationships should not be underestimated. One suggestion to decrease the workload of the supervisor even more during the project execution could be to make use of online materials to prepare the students for this kind of collaboration, and provide them tools to work in a context that can be so different from what they have experienced in their previous studies.

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a case study, where students from Aalborg University worked with the Sustainable Development Goals in a semester project in collaboration with the not-for-profit organisation Green Shoots. While the content of the project focused on bringing IT-supported Math education to learners in previously disadvantaged areas around the Western Cape, the project also provided valuable insight into how such students' projects, where the outcome benefit people and communities suffering from socio-economic challenges e.g. poverty can be carried out. In addition to demonstrate that such projects are actually possible, we studied three critical aspects: How to ensure a good fit between learning objectives and project outcome, how to ensure that the project creates value for the partner organisation and communities, and how to ensure that the projects can be conducted without overloading the university supervisors.

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